

Osteoporosis - causes of development, classification, symptoms, treatment and prevention

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named after Abu Ali ibn Sino

Annotation: Osteoporosis causes bones to become weak and brittle — so brittle that a fall or even mild stresses such as bending over or coughing can cause a break. Osteoporosis-related breaks most commonly occur in the hip, wrist or spine. Bone is living tissue that is constantly being broken down and replaced. Osteoporosis occurs when the creation of new bone doesn't keep up with the loss of old bone.

Key words: skeleton, smoking, alcohol, osteoporosis, disease, symptom, classification, metabolic, male, female, gender.

Osteoporosis is a metabolic disease of bone tissue, and it is a systemic progressive disease of the skeleton, characterized by a violation of bone microarchitecture and a decrease in their density, which causes the bone to become brittle. The reason for the development of the disease can be the long-term effect of smoking, excessive alcohol consumption, metabolic diseases, gastrointestinal diseases and other factors. Osteoporosis in the elderly develops due to poor digestion of calcium and some nutrients. The most common cause of osteoporosis is hormonal deficiency. Osteoporosis in women is usually noted during menopause. In this case,

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the disease develops not due to a lack of calcium in the body (calcium is sufficient), but due to a violation of the activity of bone-forming cells. These events occur due to hormonal imbalance, so in such cases, women should consult a gynecologist and, if necessary, receive hormonal therapy. Brittleness of bones with age is a natural physiological phenomenon. However, in some people, these processes occur at a rapid pace. This can be caused by some factors, including:

Belonging to the female gender;

European or Mongoloid race;

Thinness of the bones;

Old age (over 65 years old);

Genetic predisposition to diseases;

Vitamin D deficiency;

Frequent intake of certain drugs (for example, corticosteroids and anticonvulsants);

A sedentary lifestyle;

Smoking;

Excessive consumption of alcohol;

Diseases of the digestive system;

Dysfunction of ovaries;

Changes in the hormonal background during the climax;

Irregularities in the functioning of the adrenal glands;

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Other diseases of the endocrine glands.

Age-related (senile) osteoporosis develops due to calcium deficiency - when the rate of bone breakdown exceeds the rate of new bone formation. This form of osteoporosis usually affects people over 70 years of age. According to statistics, senile osteoporosis occurs almost twice as often in women, and in more than 95% of cases it is associated with the climactic period. Less than 5 percent of osteoporosis is due to other diseases or the use of certain drugs. This is a form of secondary osteoporosis that develops as a result of diseases of the kidneys, endocrine glands, and other diseases that lead to structural and functional diseases of bone tissue. An idiopathic form of osteoporosis is also distinguished (mainly in young people). This is a very rare disease, the cause of which is currently unknown. Idiopathic osteoporosis can develop in babies, children and young people with normal hormones. In addition, such people do not have diseases that lead to the development of osteoporosis.

Depending on the distribution, the following are distinguished:

Local osteoporosis;

Systemic osteoporosis.

Depending on the cause, osteoporosis is divided into the following cases:

Primary (associated with natural aging processes in the body):

Postmenopausal (type I);

Senile (type II);

Idiopathic (in middle-aged and underage children).

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Secondary (due to illness or external reasons):

Rheumatic diseases, connective tissue pathology (systemic lupus erythematosus, rheumatoid arthritis, Bekhterev's disease);

In endocrine pathologies;

With blood diseases;

Pathology of the gastrointestinal tract;

With kidney pathology;

With other diseases and conditions.

According to morphological criteria:

Trabecular (loss of connective tissue);

Cortical (loss of cortical substance);

A mix.

The disease can be hidden for a long time. Often the disease affects the vertebral bodies. When one vertebra is fractured, the disease is often asymptomatic, and the pain syndrome occurs as a result of multiple vertebral body fractures. The most characteristic symptoms of osteoporotic spinal injuries are pain syndrome and spinal deformity (curvature). The pain appears acutely and spreads along the spine to the front wall of the abdominal cavity. Attacks are usually triggered by sudden twisting of the body, coughing, jumping, stumbling, or lifting weights. In the morning, the pains are weak, increase during the day, and decrease a little when lying down. Testosterone drugs are prescribed when men have a low level of testosterone in their blood. Direct bone fractures caused by osteoporosis should

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also be repaired. When a hip bone is broken, a part of the bone often requires a prosthesis. If the spine is broken, immobilization is performed, painkillers and physiotherapy are used, but often the pain lasts for a long time. When the bones of the wrist are broken, the bones are repositioned and plastered. Complications of osteoporosis and prevention of the disease The main complications of osteoporosis are fractures of the spine and peripheral bones, which leads to discomfort, temporary disability and increased mortality. Maintaining physical activity, abstaining from alcohol and smoking, getting enough sleep, maintaining a moderate amount of calcium in the diet (average 1200-1500 mg per day) and vitamin D will help prevent the disease. Also, it should be exposed to enough sunlight.

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